

CONNECTION OF CREATIVE THINKING AND PHYSICS

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Annotation: The article covers the important information about relationship between connection of creative thinking and physics. On the other hand, types of creative thinking and its special features were highlighted.

Key words: *global challenges, Analysis, Open-Mindedness, Problem-Solving, catalyst, explore alternatives, Innovation, Curiosity, pedagogical strategies.*

Learning skills are important in the 21st century. These skills are required by students to cope with the rapid changes in people's life along with advances in science and technology. In this regard, educational institutions are required to prepare learners to face with global challenges. Interaction with the social community and technological advancement encourages teachers to use all their abilities to produce qualified graduates that make creation in the community environment. The qualified graduates are developed by someone who has good the skills. The skills are part of one's creative thinking or known as creative thinking skill (CTS) which are managed by memory in the form of planning or ideas and included in a quality product. Thus, CTS is a life skill that plays an important role in developing the quality of human life or society and one's long-term success. Creative thinking means thinking outside the box. Often, creativity involves lateral thinking, which is the ability to perceive patterns that are not obvious. Creative thinking might mean devising new ways to carry out tasks, solve problems, and meet challenges. It means bringing a fresh, and

sometimes unorthodox, perspective to your work. This way of thinking can help departments and organizations be more productive. Creative thinking is expressed in several ways. Here are some types of creative thinking you might see in the workplace.

- Analysis

Before thinking creatively about something, you first have to be able to understand it. This requires the ability to examine things carefully to know what they mean. Whether you are looking at a text, a data set, a lesson plan, or an equation, you need to be able to analyze it first.

- Open-Mindedness

To think creatively, set aside any assumptions or biases you may have, and look at things in a completely new way. By coming to a problem with an open mind, you allow yourself the chance to think creatively.

- Problem-Solving

Employers want creative employees who will help them to solve work-related issues. When faced with a problem, consider ways that you can solve it before asking for help. If you need the input of a manager, suggest solutions rather than just presenting problems.

Organization

This might seem counterintuitive: Aren't creative people known for being somewhat disorganized? Actually, organization is an essential part of creativity. While you might need to get a bit messy when trying out a new idea, you need to organize your ideas so others will understand and follow through with your vision.

Communication

People will only appreciate your creative idea or solution if you communicate it effectively. You need to have strong written and oral communication skills.

Creative thinking is a skill that transcends disciplinary boundaries and is

indispensable in the modern world. It is a catalyst for innovation, enabling individuals to devise unique solutions to complex problems. In the realm of physics education, practical classes offer a unique platform to nurture and enhance creative thinking among students. This article investigates various approaches to increase the level of creative thinking in students during practical physics classes.

The Role of Creative Thinking in Physics[2]:

1. Innovation: Physics is at the forefront of innovation, and creative thinking is the driving force behind groundbreaking discoveries. Practical classes in physics provide students with opportunities to explore phenomena and devise inventive solutions to problems, fostering a spirit of innovation that extends beyond the classroom.

2. Problem-Solving: Creative thinking is essential for effective problem-solving. In practical physics classes, students encounter real-world scenarios that require them to think critically, explore alternatives, and devise creative solutions. These problem-solving skills acquired in physics classes can be applied to various life situations.

Creativity and innovation are aspects that are given attention by many countries nowadays[3]. Below we are going to analyze the pedagogical Strategies for Enhancing Creative Thinking:

1. Open-Ended Projects: Encouraging students to engage in open-ended projects, where there is no single correct solution, fosters creative thinking. These projects can be based on real-world issues or phenomena, requiring students to design their experiments, analyze results, and develop innovative solutions.

2. Exploration and Curiosity: Physics classes should promote curiosity and exploration. Encouraging students to question, investigate, and experiment helps them develop a sense of wonder about the physical world. Curious

minds are more likely to engage in creative thinking.

3. Interdisciplinary Approach: Integrating elements from other disciplines, such as mathematics, engineering, and computer science, into physics practical classes can stimulate creative thinking. Students are exposed to diverse perspectives and techniques, broadening their problem-solving toolkit.

Physics as a creative subject helps in maintaining and creating a stable economic growth. Chad, (2017) noted that physics is an intensely creative endeavor, involving finding unique approaches to problems that are impractical by other means[4]. Practical physics classes are a fertile ground for nurturing creative thinking in students. Creative thinking is vital in promoting innovation and effective problem-solving, skills that are essential in the contemporary world. By employing pedagogical strategies that encourage open-ended projects, curiosity, and interdisciplinary approaches, educators can elevate the creative thinking abilities of their students. The interplay between hands-on experiments and creative thinking not only deepens students' conceptual understanding of physics but also equips them with the skills necessary to tackle the multifaceted challenges of the 21st century. Practical physics classes, when designed to foster creative thinking, serve as a cornerstone in preparing students to be innovative, adaptable, and proficient thinkers in their future academic and professional pursuits.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that the creativity is perceived as the capacity of human intelligence. The biggest challenge faced by students in developing creativity is less confidence and ashamed than their friends who have better ability. In relation, the UN agency of UNESCO's education sector called for teachers to give students opportunity to express themselves in expressing good ideas. In the classroom, community learning can serve as a space for managing abilities of all students' in generating original ideas or ideas. It can be developed if the students get a good coaching. The trainer is the teacher itself,

who provides space and movement for the students to learn and discover, and trigger the right one where students need intensive mentoring. The results show that, if teachers facilitate students in developing creativity, it has a positive impact on learning outcomes and problem solving in everyday life.

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